

EMVA 1288 Data Sheet m0637

This datasheet describes the specification according to the standard 1288 for “Characterization and Presentation of Specification Data for Image Sensors and Cameras of the European Machine Vision Association (EMVA)” (see www.standard1288.org or the *Zenodo EMVA 1288 community*) release 3.0 with proprietary extensions from AEON. The measurements were performed with the AEON ACC2b RGB-IR, Release 5, 27.06.2014, SN 0009(HCI) . The performance parameters and estimated accuracy of the measurements are described in the technical report for the instrument, its calibration in the corresponding specification and calibration report.

Measurements performed by B Jähne, HCI, Heidelberg University and H Herrmann, AEON

Vendor	IDS	Type of data presented	Single
Model	UI306xCP-M	Operation point 1, (page 5)	
Serial number	4102839784	Wavelength centroid	465.8 nm
Sensor diagonal	13.40 mm	Wavelength FWHM	20.9 nm
Lens category	C-Mount	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
Resolution	1936 × 1216, 12 bit	Operation point 2, (page 20)	
Pixel size	5.86 μm × 5.86 μm	Wavelength centroid	533.9 nm
Sensor	Sony IMX174	Wavelength FWHM	31.3 nm
Sensor type	CMOS	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
Shutter type	Global shutter	Operation point 3, (page 35)	
Overlap capabilities	Overlapping	Wavelength centroid	630.1 nm
Maximum frame rate	80.0 Hz	Wavelength FWHM	13.2 nm
Interface type	USB3 Vision	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
		Optional data measured	
		None	

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 1

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	28.6°C
Exposure time	501.00 μs	Camera body temperature	37.0°C
Frame rate	63.9 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	466 nm, 20.9 nm

Photon transfer m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

SNR m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Quantum efficiency

η 72.0%

Overall system gain

K 0.124 DN/e
 $1/K$ 8.091 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 0.81 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.12 DN
 σ_d 6.09 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.99 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 181
45.2 dB
7.5 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.55 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.49 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.49%
LE_{min} -0.59%
LE_{max} 0.39%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 9.78 p
0.285 p/μm²
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 45769 p
1333 p/μm²
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 7.04 e
0.205 e /μm²
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 32937 e
959 e /μm²

Dynamic range

DR 4680
73.4 dB
12.2 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ 2.2 DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ 18.0 e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ 19.0 e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 2

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	28.6°C
Exposure time	501.00 μ s	Camera body temperature	37.0°C
Frame rate	63.9 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	534 nm, 31.3 nm

Quantum efficiency
 η 69.5%

Overall system gain
 K 0.123 DN/e
 $1/K$ 8.108 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU
 $\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 0.80 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.12 DN
 σ_d 6.09 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 1.00 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU
SNR_{max} 181
45.2 dB
7.5 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.55 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.48 %

Nonlinearity
LE 0.34%
LE_{min} -0.40%
LE_{max} 0.29%

Sensitivity & saturation
 $\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 10.13 p
0.295 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 47234 p
1376 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 7.04 e
0.205 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 32827 e
956 e / μm^2

Dynamic range
DR 4662
73.4 dB
12.2 bit

Dark current
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 3

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	1.0, 0
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	28.6°C
Exposure time	501.00 μs	Camera body temperature	37.0°C
Frame rate	63.9 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	—
Data transfer mode	Mono 12	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	630 nm, 13.2 nm

Quantum efficiency	
η	50.8%
Overall system gain	
K	0.123 DN/e
$1/K$	8.108 e /DN
Temporal dark noise & DSNU	
$\sigma_{y, dark}$	0.81 DN
DSNU ₁₂₈₈	0.12 DN
σ_d	6.11 e
DSNU ₁₂₈₈	1.00 e
Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU	
SNR _{max}	181
	45.2 dB
	7.5 bit
$1/\text{SNR}_{max}$	0.55 %
PRNU ₁₂₈₈	0.53 %
Nonlinearity	
LE	0.53%
LE _{min}	-0.64%
LE _{max}	0.41%
Sensitivity & saturation	
$\mu_{p, min}$	13.91 p
	0.405 p/μm²
$\mu_{p, sat}$	64846 p
	1888 p/μm²
$\mu_{e, min}$	7.07 e
	0.206 e /μm²
$\mu_{e, sat}$	32941 e
	959 e /μm²
Dynamic range	
DR	4662
	73.4 dB
	12.2 bit
Dark current	
$\mu_{c, mean}$	— DN/s
$\mu_{c, mean}$	— e /s
$\mu_{c, var}$	— e /s

Detailed Data Operating Point 1, 466 nm

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1.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.030	0.030	0.031	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.031	0.030
0.016	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.015
0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002
0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001
0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.002

1.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

1.3 Linearity

Linearity m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Linearity curve.

Deviation linearity m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Deviation from linearity.

1.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

1.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 7.4 - 8.2 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.5\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram PRNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated log histogram PRNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.034%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.034%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0637, 466 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	7.80	0.81	0.12	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	407.09	7.31	1.98	0.32	0.61	0.15	30.80
20	815.50	10.28	4.01	0.45	0.71	0.09	17.65
30	1242.98	12.73	6.29	0.56	0.92	0.07	14.70
40	1636.61	14.40	8.25	0.64	1.02	0.06	12.35
50	2042.74	15.93	10.06	0.70	0.01	0.00	0.07
60	2435.49	17.16	11.61	0.76	1.59	0.07	13.72
70	2840.23	18.45	13.34	0.82	2.82	0.10	21.15
80	3235.58	19.72	15.23	0.87	3.72	0.11	24.40
90	3624.98	20.76	17.05	0.92	4.18	0.12	24.50
100	4008.13	21.64	18.85	0.96	4.28	0.11	22.70

Detailed Data Operating Point 2, 534 nm

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2.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.024	0.025	0.024	0.025	0.025	0.024	0.024	0.025
0.014	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.013	0.013
0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.004
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.003
0.002	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.002
0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.003
0.005	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.003	0.004
0.004	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.003
0.004	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.003
0.002	0.003	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004
0.003	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.003
0.004	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.002	0.003	0.004

2.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

2.3 Linearity

Linearity m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Linearity curve.

Deviation linearity m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Deviation from linearity.

2.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

2.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 7.4 - 8.2 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.5\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.035%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.035%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0637, 534 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	7.80	0.81	0.12	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	411.40	7.34	1.95	0.32	0.61	0.15	31.55
20	804.99	10.21	3.86	0.45	0.71	0.09	18.34
30	1218.09	12.60	6.00	0.56	0.92	0.08	15.27
40	1628.30	14.36	8.04	0.63	1.02	0.06	12.63
50	2034.30	15.89	9.81	0.70	0.03	0.00	0.33
60	2437.16	17.14	11.36	0.76	1.61	0.07	14.20
70	2837.61	18.42	13.04	0.81	2.84	0.10	21.79
80	3224.85	19.66	14.85	0.87	3.73	0.12	25.14
90	3614.48	20.71	16.64	0.92	4.21	0.12	25.30
100	4009.17	21.63	18.46	0.96	4.32	0.11	23.43

Detailed Data Operating Point 3, 630 nm

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3.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.029	0.028	0.027	0.028	0.028	0.028	0.028	0.029
0.014	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.014	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.014
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002
0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002
0.002	0.002	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0007):

1.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.002
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000

3.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 201 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 201 illumination steps.

3.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

3.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

3.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 7.4 - 8.2 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.04 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.034%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.034%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0637, 630 nm, 18.07.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	7.80	0.81	0.12	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	416.27	7.38	2.18	0.33	0.62	0.15	28.42
20	833.59	10.39	4.42	0.46	0.71	0.09	16.02
30	1235.46	12.68	6.68	0.56	0.92	0.07	13.76
40	1638.67	14.39	8.86	0.64	1.02	0.06	11.46
50	2039.48	15.90	10.82	0.70	0.04	0.00	0.35
60	2434.94	17.13	12.56	0.76	1.60	0.07	12.72
70	2825.95	18.38	14.41	0.81	2.79	0.10	19.35
80	3215.04	19.61	16.44	0.87	3.69	0.11	22.45
90	3603.49	20.67	18.43	0.91	4.17	0.12	22.64
100	3988.86	21.57	20.38	0.95	4.29	0.11	21.06

Comparative Evaluation with all Colors

This whole section is in extension to the EMVA 1288 standard.

Comparative characteristic curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Comparative photon transfer curve for all measured color/channel combinations.

Comparative double-logarithmic SNR curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Color dependency of PRNU: profile of middle row of sensor, shown as deviation from PRNU averaged over all measured colors.

Dark Current

Dark current from mean m0637, 18.07.2015

Mean of dark signal versus exposure time.

Dark current from variance m0637, 18.07.2015

Variance of dark signal versus exposure time.

Spatial variation of dark current (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e^-/s from mean values

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of dark current in e^-/s from variance

Comments